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IN PROCESS INDUSTRY
EEM2023**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

**JAHORINA
MARCH 20-23, 2023**

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LEAD AS BIOMARKER OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION AMONG MALE PATIENTS WITH LUNG ADENOCARCINOMA IN VOJVODINA

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Abstract

Lead (Pb) is widespread used industrial pollutant which causes extensive environmental contamination. Historically, the main source of lead emissions to the air was motor vehicle exhaust due to leaded gasoline. Although lead has been removed from gasoline, air emissions declined, it is present in the soil and can get resuspended into the air. Lead can enter the body after being inhaled or ingested with lead-contaminated food. Once it enters the body, lead is deposited in the bones where it is accumulated. Lung cancer is leading cause of all cancer deaths accounting 1 out of 5 cancer deaths or 1.8 million deaths a year globally. Lead exposure is associated with enhanced risk for lung cancer. In this research 36 male patients (39-84 years old) with inoperable IIIB and IV stadium of lung adenocarcinoma, diagnosed in the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Serbia provided morning urine samples. The presence of lead was determined by ICP-MS in their morning urine samples. In 19,44% (7/36) urine samples Pb was detected above the limit of quantification. The maximal urinary concentration was 14.89 µg/L. In order to take dilution into account the lead levels were expressed in µg/g creatinine and thus the maximal Pb urinary level was up to 90.14 µg/g creatinine. The possible sources of lead emissions today are ore and metals processing, lead smelters, leaded aviation gasoline as well as waste incinerators, utilities, and lead-acid battery manufacturers. It is worthy to note that the highest urinary levels of Pb were found in retired professional driver, while the second highest urinary Pb concentration was detected in retired refinery worker. Despite being removed from gasoline, lead is still an important environmental pollutant that can be associated with lung cancer.

Key words: pollution; lung cancer; adenocarcinoma; epidemiological study

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